

TO ASSESSMENT OF CLIMATE-RESILIENT MANAGEMENT STRATEGY FOR POD BORER *HELICOVERPA ARMIGERA* (HUBNER) IN CHICKPEA UNDER FIELD CONDITION IN MADHYA PRADESH

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ABSTRACT

The gram pod borer (*H. armigera*) is the major limiting factor for chickpea cultivation, especially in areas with high production levels. This pest has caused heavy economic losses recently due to climate change – specifically in India. It is important to understand the principles behind developing a chickpea cultivar that will resist or develop tolerance with manipulation of recommended agronomical practices against this pest. This experiment was carried out at Research Farm of Soybean Seed Production-Unit, College of Agriculture, JNKVV (MP) during *Rabi* season 2019-20 and 2020-21. The field experiment was laid out in split split plot design with 24 treatments and three replications. The observation on number of eggs and larval population of *H. armigera* were recorded from one-meter row length (mrl). The percent of pod damage was computed by the total number of pods and damage pod per plant. In this study, it was found that varieties JG 14 and 24 chickpeas were the most resilient to damage by *H. armigera* when crop sown on November 15th with one irrigation, relative to other tested varieties. The highest seed yield was also observed in these same cultivars.

Key words: Date of sowings, irrigation levels, chickpea varieties, egg counts, larval population and pod damage by *H. armigera* and seed yield

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1. INTRODUCTION

Chickpea (*Cicer arietinum* L.) is one of the most important pulse crops of the *rabi* season cultivated mainly in semi-arid and warm temperature regions of the world. Madhya Pradesh ranks first among both area and production in India. In India during 2017-18, Chickpea was cultivated in about 10.56 million hectares, with a production of about 11.23 million tons with a productivity of 1063 kg/ha (Anon, 2018). Chickpea was cultivated in about 3.59 million hectares with a production of 4.59 million tons with a productivity of 1282 kg/ha in Madhya Pradesh's state (Anon, 2018).

The gram pod borer (*H. armigera*) is one of the most detrimental insect pests of chickpea causing heavy economic losses to the crop in every year from the germination to the harvest of the crop. It causes loss ranging from 30 to 80 percent, especially due to recent changes in India's climate (NCIPM, 2014). The continuous presence of single larva per meter row during the pod formation stage of the crop resulted in 6.9% pod damage, 6.2% grain damage, and 5.4% yield loss due to recent changes in State climate (Ambulkar, 2011). Global warming and climate change reported to will have a major limitation and will enhance pest incidence and pest associated losses in field crops. Therefore, studies on pest incidence in chickpea across sowing dates to understand the effect of climatic factors on pest incidence and its on crop performance. The egg-laying by the pod borer, *H. armigera*, decreased across sowing dates from October to December, with a slight increase in oviposition was observed in the January sown crops. This pest preferred some cultivars for egg-laying. The pest was less severe in early sown crop and its incidence and impact was more in late sown crop (Pavani et al., 2018). Number of chemical insecticides are being use injudiciously, this led to development of resistance in insects, secondary pest outbreaks, threat to their natural enemies and residual effect on the environment. To overcome the above threats, some workers have advocated that agronomical practices like altering the sowing date might be a possible resort to escape chickpea crop from this pest (Singh et al., 2002). Managing pests in a sustainable way can be economically feasible, practical and resilient to climate change. By achieving high quantum yields of pest-resistant or tolerant varieties through appropriate timing, farmers may suffer less economic losses from pod borer incidence. However, by adopting climate smart management strategies that include sowing resistant/tolerant varieties with recommended agricultural modifications, the desired outcome may be achievable at a lower cost overall. Therefore, the present study was designed in order to assess climate resilient management strategy for Pod borer *H. armigera* in different chickpea varieties under field condition.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Experimental site and layout

The field experiment was conducted during *rabi* season of 2019-20 and 2020-21 at Research Farm of Breeding Seed Production-Soybean, Unit of College of Agriculture, Jawaharlal Nehru Krishi Vishwa Vidyalaya, Jabalpur (M.P.). The experimental site lies between 23° 10' N latitude and 79° 56' E longitude, and 411.78 m above mean sea level. The field experiment was laid out in split split plot design with 24 treatments and three replications. The treatments included three dates of sowing, *i.e.*, 15th November, 30th November, and 15th December as the main plot, two irrigation levels, *i.e.*, I₀-no irrigation and I₁- irrigation at 35 DAS as sub plots and four chickpea varieties *i.e.*, JG 12, JG 36, JG 14 and JG 24 as sub sub plots. The treatments were randomly allocated in each replication.

2.2 Observations on eggs and larval population of *H. armigera*

Weekly observations were recorded on the number of *H. armigera* eggs and larvae from one-meter row length (mrl) at five randomly selected places from the field emergence stage to the crop harvest from each plot. The counts recorded from five randomly selected places were averaged separately for each plot and made into the number of eggs and larvae per meter row length (mrl).

2.3 Pod damage

The total number of pods and damage pod per plant were recorded at the harvest time based on randomly selected five places in each plot, and the average value was calculated. The percent of pod damage was computed by using the following formula:

$$\text{Percent Pod Damage} = \frac{\text{Total number of pods}}{\text{Total number of damaged pods}} \times 100$$

2.4 Seed yield

Seed yield (kg plot⁻¹) After threshing, winnowing, and sun drying, each plot's seed yield was recorded separately in "kilogram" and converted into kg ha⁻¹.

2.5 Data analysis

Statistical analysis was performed to test the variation of yield with different treatments. The data recorded on different observations were tabulated and analyzed statistically using the techniques of analysis of variance (ANOVA) by online software OPSTAT.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the present investigation egg count, larval population, pod damage by *H. armigera*, and Seed yield to different chickpea varieties were significantly affected by different sowing dates and irrigation levels, shown in table 1 and graphically presented in figure 1. The early sowing environment was congenial for avoiding egg laying, larval population by the *H. armigera* thereby least pod damage and favorable for the pods development and seed yield. Crop sown on 15th November was recorded the significantly overall minimum mean eggs (0.49 eggs/mrl), larval population (0.97 larvae/mrl) and pod damage plant⁻¹ (9.59 %) as compared to 30th November and 15th December sowing while the seed yield (2,334.26 kg/ha) was increased significantly. Confirm with the present finding, Parmar et al. (2015) reported that the incidence and population fluctuation of *Helicoverpa armigera* was much dependent on the prevailed weather parameters during cropping season of all seven different dates of sowing. The overall minimum mean eggs and larval population was recorded on early sown crop on November 07, which was significantly superior over the other sowing dates. Ambulkar et al. (2011) also reported that, 28th October and 20th November sowing time exhibited lowest larval populations, least pod damage and highest seed yield whereas 11th December sown crop showed highest larval populations, pod damage and lower seed yield. Similarly, Singh et al. (2002) noted the later sown crop of Chickpea suffered most from the *H. armigera* and yielded less than the earlier sown crop. The treatment receiving one irrigation at 35 DAS was found significantly the least eggs count (0.90 eggs/mrl), larval population (1.52 larvae/mrl) and pod damage plant⁻¹ (12.22 %), whereas the highest seed yield (2,040.28 kg/ha) was observed significantly over no irrigation. This might be due to the effect of ecological variation on chickpea varieties. Similarly, Parabhakar et al (1998) studied the damage potential and economic threshold for *H. armigera* larvae on chickpea under irrigated and unirrigated conditions and reported that on average, a single larva in one metre row length reduced the yield to the extent of 91.00 kg/ha under unirrigated conditions and 87.62 kg/ha under irrigated conditions. Larva per m row was 1.02 and 0.79 in unirrigated and irrigated conditions, respectively. Ambulkar et al. (2011) also observed that maximum larval populations and pod damage were recorded when irrigation was not applied while the minimum seed yield was obtained.

JG 14 variety exhibited significant lowest mean eggs and larval population (0.42 eggs/mrl & 0.98 larvae/mrl respectively) of *H. armigera* while 24 chickpea variety exhibited least Pod damage by *H. armigera* plant⁻¹ (11.09%) and highest yield (2,034.26 kg/ha) which were at par with JG 14 variety. This might be due to the fact that physiological and biological mechanism which is responsible for insect resistance is present in JG 14 and JG 24 variety. Conformity with the present finding, Brar (2014) studied the oviposition-preference of *H. armigera* on nine genotypes of chickpea in multiple-choice tests under field conditions. The mean number of eggs pooled over six weeks showed that genotype 5282 recorded the lowest number of eggs and was statistically at par with genotype ICCL 86111, RSG 963 GL 25016. Kumar et al. (2013) also screened 50 genotypes of chickpea against *H. armigera* under field conditions. The lowest larval population and lowest pod damage were recorded in resistant genotype C 235. Nadeem et al. (2010) recorded varietal resistance in 13 advanced Desi chickpea genotypes against chickpea pod borer, *H. armigera* during 2007-2008 and reported that among the tested genotypes, B 8/03, CH 4/02, and CH 9/02 had less larval population per plant, minimum pod damage and highest seed yield, with an increase of 256.8 to 285.7% with respect to check. Deshmukh et al. (2010) screened of chickpea germplasms against pod borer, *H. armigera* (Huber) and found that BG-372, HC-1, SAKI-9516, Vijay and Avrodhi were comparatively less susceptible as these harbored lower larval population also had lower damage to pods and higher seed yield than remaining cultivars.

4. CONCLUSION

The use of pest resistant or tolerant varieties at the optimum time is economically viable, feasible, and climate-resilient option to manage pest from a farmer's point of view; this can be most acceptable from pest control techniques. However, such high quantum yield and farmers' economic losses can be lowered by adopting climate-smart pest management strategies, including the sowing of pest-resistant/tolerant variety at the optimum time supported with recommended agronomic manipulations. The present study found that variety JG 14 and 24 chickpeas were the most resilient to damage by *H. armigera* when sown on 15th November with one irrigation, compared to other varieties tested. The highest seed yield was also observed in the same varieties.

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Table:1 Overall egg & larval population, Pod damage by *H. armigera* and seed yield in different chickpea varieties as influenced by sowing dates and irrigation levels (mean of 2019-20 and 2020-21)

Treatment	overall eggs/mrl	overall larvae/mrl	% Pod damage	Seed yield (Kg/ha)
D ₁ (15 Th Nov.)	0.49 (0.98)	0.97 (1.20)	9.59 (17.88)	2,334.26
D ₂ (30 Th Nov.)	0.88 (1.16)	1.50 (1.41)	11.22 (19.40)	1,854.40
D ₃ (15 Th Dec.)	1.56 (1.40)	2.31 (1.65)	18.57 (25.22)	1,611.58
Sem±	0.009	0.012	0.41	48.70
C.D. (P=0.05)	0.035	0.047	1.60	190.15
I ₀ (no irrigation)	1.05 (1.21)	1.67 (1.44)	14.03 (21.54)	1,826.54
I ₁ (irrigation at 35DAS)	0.90 (1.15)	1.52 (1.39)	12.22 (20.13)	2,040.28
Sem±	0.006	0.005	0.29	42.13
C.D. (P=0.05)	0.017	0.014	0.83	120.28
JG12	1.67 (1.45)	2.34 (1.667)	16.52 (23.60)	1,717.90
JG36	0.97 (1.20)	1.64 (1.456)	13.05 (20.79)	1,967.59
JG14	0.42 (0.96)	0.98 (1.211)	11.84 (20.04)	2,013.89
JG24	0.85 (1.11)	1.43 (1.34)	11.09 (18.92)	2,034.26
Sem±	0.008	0.007	0.41	72.98
C.D. (P=0.05)	0.023	0.020	1.18	NS

*Mean of five samples and three replications

*Figures in parenthesis are the ark sin transformed values and $\sqrt{X + 0.5}$

Figure 1: Oviposition preference, larval population, Pod damage by *H. armigera* and seed yield influenced by different treatments